

Managing challenging waste fractions: Mechanical recycling of GFRP of wind turbine rotor blades and environmental assessment

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Article type

Note

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Abstract

The rising decommissioning of wind turbines generates significant quantities of end-of-life glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) rotor blades. While mechanical recycling offers an energy-efficient disposal alternative, the resulting recycle's suitability as a reinforcement in thermoplastic matrices remains underexplored. This study evaluates the use of mechanically recycled GFRP powder (rGFRP) from shredded and fractionated waste (0.063 mm, 0.045 mm, and <0.045 mm) as a filler in Polyamide 6 (PA6) via twin-screw compounding and injection molding. The mechanical performance of the rGFRP composites at 13 wt% and 23 wt% nominal loadings was compared against neat PA6 and virgin glass fiber composites through tensile testing, room-temperature (23 °C) Charpy impact testing, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The addition of rGFRP markedly increased the tensile modulus of PA6, reaching values of up to 4268 MPa. Most notably, the finest rGFRP fraction (< 0.045 mm) at 23 wt% yielded a mean room-temperature impact strength of 22.33 ± 3.02 kJ/m², which was comparable to or even higher than that of virgin glass-fiber references (19.64 ± 1.68 kJ/m²), despite the lower actual inorganic fiber content. This enhancement is hypothesized to result from the residual epoxy matrix adhering to the recycled glass fibers, which may improve mechanical interlocking with the PA6 matrix. Fiber length analysis of the ashed specimens confirmed that all recycle fractions retain median fiber lengths (D50) between 44.5 and 89.9 μm after processing. A comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) indicates that the mechanical recycling approach can achieve net-negative environmental impacts when the reclaimed fibers substitute virgin glass fiber production. The results indicate that mechanically recycled wind turbine blades can effectively reinforce PA6, offering a promising circular economy approach for upcycling complex thermoset composite waste into valuable secondary materials.

Keywords

Wind turbine blades, Mechanical recycling, Glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP), Polyamide 6 composites, Circular economy

1. Introduction

The global transition toward renewable energy has driven an exponential increase in wind power installations over the past two decades. Consequently, the wind energy sector is now confronting a significant end-of-life (EoL) challenge. Wind turbine rotor blades, predominantly constructed from glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) based on thermoset resins like epoxy, have a typical operational lifespan of 20 to 25 years [1]. As the first generation of large-scale wind farms reaches decommissioning, thousands of tons of GFRP waste are generated annually. Due to their cross-linked chemical structure, thermoset matrix and the corresponding composites cannot be simply remelted and reshaped, making their disposal highly problematic. Historically, landfilling and incineration have been the primary disposal routes, however, tightening environmental regulations and the drive toward a circular economy necessitate the development of viable recycling strategies [2] [3] [4].

Current recycling technologies for GFRP are broadly categorized into thermal (e.g., pyrolysis, fluidized bed), chemical (e.g., solvolysis), and mechanical processes [5] [6]. While thermal and chemical methods can recover relatively clean glass fibers, they are highly energy-intensive and often degrade the mechanical properties of the recovered fibers. An economic comparison by Liu et al. identified mechanical recycling and fluidized-bed recycling as the optimal ready-to-go technologies for blade waste management [3]. Mechanical recycling, which involves crushing, shredding, and milling the composite waste into powders or fibrous fractions, offers a more energy-efficient and scalable alternative [7] [8]. However, the resulting recyclate is a heterogeneous mixture of glass fibers and residual cured matrix, which poses challenges for its re-integration into new product streams.

One promising pathway for valorizing mechanical GFRP recyclates is their use as reinforcing fillers in thermoplastic matrices. Previous studies have demonstrated that mechanically recycled wind turbine blade material can be successfully compounded with thermoplastic resins such as high density polyethylene (HDPE) [9], acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) [10], and polypropylene [11]. For PA6 — a widely used engineering polymer known for its excellent mechanical properties, thermal stability, and processability — early work by Pedroso et al. showed that recycled GF/PA6 composites can retain or even improve impact strength despite fiber shortening [12]. By compounding GFRP recyclate into PA6, it is theoretically possible to close the loop, creating secondary composite materials for injection molding applications [13] [14] [15].

Despite the potential of this approach, there is a critical research gap regarding the systematic evaluation of how the specific particle size and the presence of residual epoxy matrix in mechanically recycled rotor blade material affect the mechanical performance of the resulting thermoplastic composites. While the degradation of fiber length and matrix properties through repeated mechanical recycling has been well documented for glass fiber reinforced polyamides [16] [17], no study to date has systematically investigated the use of fractionated, mechanically recycled wind turbine blade powder as a filler in PA6.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to comprehensively investigate the influence of mechanically recycled glass fibers from end-of-life wind turbine rotor blades on the mechanical properties of PA6 composites. By fractionating the recycled material into specific particle sizes and comparing its performance against virgin glass fibers at different loading levels (13 wt% and 23 wt%), this research aims to elucidate the structure-property relationships of these secondary materials. Particular emphasis is placed on evaluating room-temperature (23 °C) impact strength, stiffness, and fiber-matrix interfacial interactions, providing crucial insights for the industrial upcycling of wind energy waste.

2. Materials and Methods

An overview of the experimental methodology, from the end-of-life rotor blades to the characterization of the injection-molded composites, is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the mechanical recycling and composite manufacturing process.

PA6 (Wellamid 6000 SCP, CP-Polymer-Technik GmbH & Co. KG) was utilized as the primary polymer matrix for all composite formulations. To establish a comparative baseline, two types of virgin glass fibers were employed: 3 mm ECR-glass fibers and 0.2 mm E-glass fibers. For the recycled reinforcement, end-of-life glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) wind turbine rotor blades were sourced and subjected to a mechanical recycling process. The resulting mechanically recycled GFRP powder is hereafter referred to as rGFRP.

2.1. Preparation of recycled glass fibres

The GFRP rotor blades (see Figure 2) were initially reduced in size using an industrial twin-shaft shredder (JBF HD 38/54). The resulting comminuted material consisted of a mixture of glass fibers and residual cross-linked epoxy matrix. To systematically evaluate the influence of particle size, the shredded recyclate was fractionated using a multi-stage sieving process (Retsch AS 200 Digit CA analytical sieving machine). Three distinct size fractions were isolated for compounding: a coarse fraction retained on a 0.063 mm sieve mesh (> 0.063 mm, hereafter referred to as the 0.063 mm fraction), a medium fraction passing the 0.063 mm sieve but retained on a 0.045 mm mesh (0.045–0.063 mm, referred to as the 0.045 mm fraction), and a fine fraction passing through the 0.045 mm mesh (< 0.045 mm). Particle size distributions were analyzed using a PowderShape system (IST AG).

Figure 2: Dismantling of the wind turbine whose rotor blades were used in this study.

2.2. Compounding and injection molding

Composite materials were prepared using a twin-screw extruder (Process 16, Thermo Fisher Scientific). A systematic comparative study was conducted, evaluating the different fiber types (virgin and the three rGFRP fractions) at two nominal filler contents: 13 wt% and 23 wt%. Due to the presence of residual thermoset matrix in the rGFRP fractions, the rheological behavior during extrusion differed from that of the virgin fibers. The extruder exit zone temperature was set to 250–260 °C for the rGFRP fractions at screw speeds of 120–155 rpm. For the virgin 0.2 mm E-glass fibers, the exit zone temperature was higher (270–275 °C, 125–135 rpm), while the virgin 3 mm ECR-glass fibers required the lowest exit zone temperature (220–240 °C, 120–130 rpm) due to the different feeding and melting behavior of the longer fibers. The screw configuration comprised conveying elements, two kneading blocks for distributive mixing, and a final conveying zone to build pressure at the die. Following extrusion, the compounded strands were cooled in a water bath, pelletized, and subsequently dried at 80 °C for a minimum of 4 h using a dry-air dryer (TTM 4/50 EST, Gerco) to reduce the moisture content below 0.1 wt% prior to further processing. Test specimens were fabricated using an Arburg Allrounder 470 E injection molding machine, conforming to standard multi-purpose test specimen geometries (ISO 3167 Type 1A). The melt mass temperature during injection molding was set to 238–245 °C for the rGFRP composites and virgin fiber composites.

2.3. Material characterisation

To determine the actual glass fiber content, ashing tests were performed in accordance with ISO 3451-1 using a muffle furnace (Carbolite Gero CWF 12/65). Three specimens per formulation were heated to 600 °C and held for 2 h until constant mass. The residual mass was recorded to quantify the inorganic fiber fraction, distinguishing it from the combustible polymer and epoxy matrix. Mechanical properties were evaluated through tensile and impact testing. Five specimens per formulation were tested to ensure statistical reliability in accordance with the standards. Tensile tests were conducted according to ISO 527 using a ZwickRoell Z030 TEW universal testing machine to determine the tensile strength and tensile modulus. The crosshead speed was set to 1 mm/min for modulus determination and 5 mm/min for tensile strength testing. Charpy impact strength was assessed according to ISO 179-1/1eU (unnotched specimens, edgewise impact) using a ZwickRoell HIT25P pendulum impact tester equipped with a 5 J pendulum hammer. The impact tests were performed at room temperature (23 °C). To characterize the residual fiber length after compounding and injection molding, the ashed residues from the fiber content determination were analyzed using a PowderShape digital microscopy system (IST AG). The median fiber length (D50) was determined from the cumulative length distribution of the measured particles. For each of the three ashing specimens per formulation, two separate image analyses were performed (one from the Charpy specimen and one from the tensile specimen), yielding six measurements per formulation (n = 6).

Finally, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was utilized to examine the fracture surfaces of the tested specimens. The samples were sputter-coated with gold using a JEOL JFC-1300 Auto Fine Coater and subsequently examined with a JEOL JSM-IT510LA scanning electron microscope operated at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Additionally, digital microscopy (Leica DVM6 A) was used for complementary optical assessments. This microstructural analysis provided insights into the fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion, fiber pull-out phenomena, and the dispersion quality of the rGFRP versus virgin fibers.

2.4. Environmental assessment

The environmental impacts were assessed by performing a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the most promising recycling approach and the current waste treatment for wind turbine blades. The system boundaries were defined using a 'cut-off' approach from the collected waste to the provision of reclaimed glass fibres. For reference, the results of the recycling approach were compared to the impacts of virgin material production and the current waste treatment based on literature information from Diez-Cañamero and Mendoza [18]. The virgin material to be replaced was modelled as virgin glass fibres. It was assumed that wind turbine blades are currently used for limestone substitution in cement production while another share is incinerated with energy recovery. Data was taken from lab-scale and semi-industrial scale complemented by literature data. Thereby, the process data for the developed mechanical recycling approach was obtained for all processes listed in Table 1. The life cycle inventories for the environmental assessment were prepared using the 'LCA For Experts' software (formerly known as 'GaBi', version 10.9.1.17) and the Managed LCA Database (formerly known as 'GaBi database', version 2025.1). More information on the life cycle inventories and underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

The environmental impacts were calculated using the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method provided by the European Commission. The results of the 16 assessed environmental impact categories that are covered by the EF 3.1 method were summarized using a normalized and weighted Single score with normalisation and weighting factors [19]. For further examination of the influence of the individual data points, a scenario analysis was carried out. In this analysis, it was assumed that not only the most promising sieving fraction can replace virgin glass fibres, but also two other fractions. Further information on the underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

Table 1: Processes modelled for the mechanical recycling approach; scale indication based on equipment throughput (semi-industrial = low end of industrial throughput)

Process	Equipment name	Data source	Scale
Pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)	Two shaft shredder JBF HD 38/54	Collected data	Semi-industrial
Sieving	Vibrating sieving machine AS 200 Digit CA Retsch GmbH	Collected (no energy data)	Lab

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Material Characterization

The actual inorganic glass fiber content of the injection-molded specimens, determined via ashing, revealed significant deviations from the nominal filler contents, particularly for the rGFRP materials (Figure 2). The virgin 0.2 mm E-glass composites closely approximated the target contents (~19 wt% and ~23 wt% for the 13% and 23% targets, respectively). In contrast, the virgin 3 mm ECR-glass at the 13 wt% target reached only 10.6 wt%, likely due to feeding difficulties associated with the longer fiber length in the small-scale extruder. For all rGFRP fractions, the actual fiber contents fell markedly below the nominal values. For the nominal 23 wt% rGFRP compounds, the actual inorganic fiber mass fractions ranged only between 10.0 wt% and 13.7 wt%. This discrepancy is attributed to the presence of residual epoxy matrix in the recyclate, which contributes to the mass of the filler during formulation but combusts during the ashing process, leaving only the pure glass fibers behind. The residual fiber lengths after compounding and injection molding, determined from image analysis of the ashed specimens, are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Median residual fiber length (D50) determined from cumulative length distributions of ashed specimens using PowderShape image analysis. Values are mean \pm standard deviation of six measurements per formulation.

Formulation	Nominal loading (wt%)	D50 (μ m)
Virgin 3 mm ECR-glass	13	79.1 \pm 4.6
Virgin 3 mm ECR-glass	23	61.1 \pm 2.6
Virgin 0.2 mm E-glass	13	74.0 \pm 5.0
Virgin 0.2 mm E-glass	23	63.3 \pm 1.9
rGFRP 0.063 mm	13	89.9 \pm 2.6
rGFRP 0.063 mm	23	72.3 \pm 5.5
rGFRP 0.045 mm	13	72.3 \pm 5.5
rGFRP 0.045 mm	23	71.6 \pm 5.0
rGFRP < 0.045 mm	13	59.7 \pm 2.0
rGFRP < 0.045 mm	23	44.5 \pm 5.8

For the virgin 3 mm ECR-glass fibers, the median residual fiber length (D50) decreased from 79.1 \pm 4.6 μ m at 13 wt% to 61.1 \pm 2.6 μ m at 23 wt%, reflecting the increased fiber breakage at higher filler loadings during processing. The virgin 0.2 mm E-glass fibers showed a similar trend (74.0 \pm 5.0 μ m at 13 wt% vs. 63.3 \pm 1.9 μ m at 23 wt%). Among the rGFRP fractions, the coarsest fraction (0.063 mm) at 13 wt% retained the longest median fiber length (89.9 \pm 2.6 μ m), while the finest fraction (< 0.045 mm) at 23 wt% exhibited the shortest fibers (44.5 \pm 5.8 μ m). Notably, even the finest rGFRP fraction at 13 wt% still retained fibers of 59.7 \pm 2.0 μ m median length, comparable to the virgin 3 mm ECR-glass at 23 wt% (61.1 μ m). The 0.045 mm fraction showed intermediate values of 72.3 \pm 5.5 μ m (13 wt%) and 71.6 \pm 5.0 μ m (23 wt%). This indicates that the mechanical recycling and sieving process, while reducing particle size, does not completely pulverize the glass fibers but retains fiber fragments of measurable length that can contribute to reinforcement.

Actual vs. Nominal Glass Fiber Content (Ashing)

Figure 3: Actual vs. nominal inorganic glass fiber content determined via ashing.

Despite this considerably lower actual glass fiber fraction in the rGFRP compounds, the mechanical stiffness remained high across all formulations. The tensile strength and tensile modulus of the composites were evaluated and compared against unreinforced neat PA6 (Figures 3 and 4). Neat PA6 exhibited a tensile strength of 56.7 MPa and a tensile modulus of 1660 MPa. The addition of both virgin and rGFRP fillers markedly increased the stiffness of the material. The highest modulus was observed in the Virgin 0.2 mm E-glass composite at 23 wt% (4930 ± 96 MPa). The rGFRP composites also demonstrated robust stiffness, with the 0.063 mm fraction at 23 wt% achieving a modulus of 4268 ± 39 MPa. This is notable because mechanical recycling typically leads to significant fiber shortening, which predominantly reduces tensile strength while the modulus — being less sensitive to fiber length above a certain critical minimum — is better preserved [16] [17]. The fiber length analysis is consistent with this interpretation: although the median fiber lengths ($D50 = 44.5\text{--}89.9$ μm) are likely below the critical fiber length for glass fiber/PA6 systems — which is typically estimated at several hundred micrometers based on Kelly-Tyson calculations [13] — the modulus contribution of sub-critical-length fibers is well established, as even short fibers increase composite stiffness through constrained matrix deformation. Conversely, the tensile strength remained relatively stable or slightly decreased compared to the neat PA6, ranging from 51.7 MPa to 59.8 MPa. The fine rGFRP fraction (< 0.045 mm) at 13 wt% exhibited the highest mean tensile strength (59.8 ± 1.0 MPa), though a formal statistical comparison was not performed to confirm whether this difference is statistically significant.

Tensile Strength of PA6 Composites

Figure 4: Tensile strength of neat PA6 and the various composite formulations.

Tensile Modulus of PA6 Composites

Figure 5: Tensile modulus of neat PA6 and the various composite formulations.

The room-temperature (23 °C) Charpy impact strength results (Figure 5) yielded the most surprising findings. Unreinforced PA6 exhibited a baseline impact strength of 9.18 kJ/m². As expected, the addition of virgin glass fibers

improved the impact resistance (up to 19.64 kJ/m² for Virgin 3 mm ECR at 23 wt%). However, the fine recycled fraction (< 0.045 mm) demonstrated exceptional performance. At a nominal 23 wt%, this rGFRP composite achieved a mean impact strength of 22.33 ± 3.02 kJ/m², numerically exceeding the best virgin fiber result (Virgin 3 mm ECR at 23 wt%: 19.64 ± 1.68 kJ/m²). However, the relatively large standard deviations and small sample size (n = 5) indicate that the overlapping confidence intervals preclude a definitive claim of statistical superiority without further testing (e.g., one-way ANOVA with post-hoc analysis). Even at the nominal 13 wt% loading, the < 0.045 mm fraction reached 21.03 ± 3.46 kJ/m². This finding is consistent with the observations of Pedroso et al., who reported a 21% increase in impact strength for recycled GF/PA6 despite a 37% reduction in average fiber length, attributing the effect to increased matrix ductility [12]. Similarly, Akay et al. demonstrated that glass fibers in PA66 increase total impact energy by 300–600% and noted that soft interlayers between fiber and matrix can reduce interfacial micro-failure initiation [20].

Charpy Impact Strength of PA6 Composites (23 °C)

Figure 6: Room-temperature (23 °C) Charpy impact strength of the composites.

Taken together, these results indicate that recycled glass fibers from end-of-life wind turbine rotor blades can serve as an effective reinforcement for PA6, with the finest fraction reaching impact strength levels comparable to those of virgin glass fiber composites. A plausible explanation for this mechanical behavior is the presence of residual cross-linked epoxy matrix on the glass fiber surfaces after mechanical shredding, since residual resin contamination of recycled fibers has been widely reported in the literature. It is proposed that the residual epoxy is not merely an inert filler but may actively participate in stress transfer. The irregular, rough surface of the shredded epoxy-glass clusters could enhance mechanical interlocking with the PA6 matrix, partially compensating for the lack of optimized chemical sizing that virgin fibers possess. Analogous toughening effects attributed to residual thermoset matrix on recycled fibers have been reported in multiscale modeling and experimental studies [21] [22]. In situ SEM tensile testing by Zheng et al. on recycled glass fiber/PP composites directly demonstrated that recycled fibers act as supporting bodies that effectively promote mass micro-cracking; the crack initiation, propagation, and fiber breakage associated with these micro-cracks dissipate substantial energy, thereby reinforcing the composite's mechanical properties [23]. Future work employing dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) would be needed to verify the exact energy-dissipation mechanisms. To further investigate these interfacial interactions, SEM analysis of the fracture surfaces (Figure 6) was conducted. The virgin fibers exhibited clean pull-out holes and relatively smooth fiber surfaces, typical of standardized sizing. In contrast, the rGFRP particles displayed irregular surfaces with residual epoxy adhering to the glass. This inherent roughness and the presence of the secondary polymer phase appear to

influence the failure mechanism, supporting the hypothesis that these microstructural features contribute to the enhanced energy absorption observed in the impact tests.

Figure 7: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images. (a) Virgin glass fibers exhibiting clean pull-out. (b) Particle surface of mechanically recycled GFRP (rGFRP) showing adhering residual epoxy matrix. (c) Fracture surface of the corresponding rGFRP composite.

Furthermore, the fractionation of the rGFRP material revealed a distinct particle size effect. The finest fraction (< 0.045 mm) exhibited the most outstanding impact strength. Smaller particle sizes provide a larger specific surface area for interfacial bonding with the PA6 matrix. Finer particles are also less likely to act as critical macroscopic flaw initiation sites under impact loading compared to larger, sharper shards of shredded GFRP. A comparable particle-size-dependent behavior was observed by Malinowski et al. for WTB waste fractions in ABS, where finely milled fractions produced composites with more consistent properties than coarser fractions [10]. The fine dispersion of these hybrid epoxy-glass particles may effectively toughen the PA6 matrix, possibly by inducing energy-dissipating mechanisms such as localized shear yielding or micro-cracking ahead of the main crack front, though direct experimental confirmation of these mechanisms remains to be established [13].

Finally, from a processing and manufacturing perspective, the substitution of virgin fibers with rGFRP powder introduces specific challenges. The presence of the thermoset residual matrix alters the melt rheology, necessitating adjustments to the compounding parameters, specifically requiring higher extrusion temperatures to maintain adequate flow. Yeole et al. similarly reported that chemical additives (dispersants, flocculants) were required to achieve homogeneous fiber distribution in recycled GF/PA6 wet-laid composites, highlighting the processing challenges inherent to recycled glass fiber systems [15]. This thermal history must be carefully managed to prevent thermal degradation of the PA6 matrix while ensuring homogeneous dispersion of the recycled filler.

3.2. Environmental assessment

For the environmental assessment, the mechanical recycling approach is compared to the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery (see Figure 8: Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and current waste treatment of 1 kg of rotor blades (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with appropriate product application). All results for the individual impact categories without normalization and weighting are provided in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 8: Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and current waste treatment of 1 kg of rotor blades (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with appropriate product application

The current waste treatment, crushing, grinding and incineration, has higher impacts, namely 1725% of the recycling impacts, and receives credits (-1515%) for recovering electricity, heat and limestone substitute in cement production. In general, it is expected that the credits for energy recovery are going to decrease in the future, when more sustainable energy production processes are substituted. Currently, the current waste disposal has 210% of the recycling impacts after totalling the impacts and credits. On the other hand, the recycling of 1 kg of rotor blades produces 60 g of reclaimed fibres for further use. An environmental credit can be achieved when these fibres can substitute the same amount of virgin glass fibres in a product application similar to the energy credits. In that case, the material credit for avoiding virgin glass fibre production (-190502%) leads to net-negative environmental impacts for the mechanical recycling approach (-190402%) that are much lower than the net impacts of the incineration process. This large credit stems from the high environmental impacts related to the production of virgin glass fibres.

When more fractions can be used, the share of reclaimed fibres can increase from 60 g to 248 g, which, according to the scenario analysis, will lead to more than four times the credit compared to only reusing the most promising fraction. All results can be found in the Supplementary information.

3.3. Limitations

While this study establishes the feasibility of using mechanically recycled rotor blade material (rGFRP) in PA6, certain limitations must be acknowledged. No formal statistical hypothesis testing (e.g., ANOVA) was performed; all comparisons are based on descriptive statistics (mean \pm standard deviation, $n = 5$). Furthermore, the research utilized a specific batch of GFRP waste, and the inherent variability of end-of-life wind turbine blades — subject to different environmental aging histories and original manufacturer specifications — could influence the consistency of future recyclates. While the median fiber length (D50) and shape factors were characterized using automated image analysis (PowderShape), true three-dimensional fiber aspect ratios (L/D) could not be determined from the two-dimensional image projections, which limits the quantitative interpretation of the reinforcement efficiency. Future research should focus on long-term durability testing, including fatigue and hygrothermal aging, to fully qualify these materials for demanding engineering applications.

Without a product application, no statements on the substitution potential for virgin PP and therefore the actual environmental benefits are possible. Also, the LCA results were calculated from a mix of available lab-scale and semi-industrial scale data and no energy consumption was available for the sieving process. The model used for the calculations represents the status quo of the recycling approach. Future implementation on a larger scale may result in different results due to an increased efficiency or different configurations of the modelled processes.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated that mechanically recycled GFRP from end-of-life wind turbine rotor blades can serve as an effective reinforcement for PA6. Four key findings emerge. First, fiber length analysis of the ashed specimens confirmed that the recycled fractions retain median fiber lengths (D50) between 44.5 and 89.9 μm after compounding and injection molding; although these lengths are likely below the critical fiber length for GF/PA6, even sub-critical fibers contribute to stiffness through constrained matrix deformation. Second, the incorporation of rGFRP markedly increased the tensile modulus of PA6 to levels comparable to those of virgin glass fiber composites, despite a lower actual inorganic fiber content caused by residual epoxy in the recyclate. Third, the finest sieved fraction (< 0.045 mm) achieved room-temperature Charpy impact strengths numerically comparable to — or exceeding — those of virgin glass fiber references, pointing to a beneficial role of the residual thermoset matrix and high specific surface area, though formal statistical confirmation is still needed. Fourth, processing rGFRP requires adapted compounding conditions (higher barrel temperatures, adjusted injection pressures) to accommodate the altered melt rheology.

The life cycle assessment shows that the developed recycling approach can lead to a reduction of the environmental impacts when the reclaimed fibers substitute virgin material. However, the net savings depend on the actual substitution.

In conclusion, mechanical size-reduction and fractionation of EoL rotor blades can produce valuable secondary raw materials. Future work should focus on optimizing the compounding process to further enhance fiber dispersion and systematically investigating the long-term durability of these sustainable composite materials.

Author **Supplementary Information**

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A Life Cycle Inventory

The life cycle inventories are listed in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The following general assumptions were applied:

- Electricity is supplied by the general German electricity mix (2022). Process water supply is modelled as tap water from groundwater.
- Residual waste is treated as commercial waste. The process 'DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery.
- Transport processes were not considered, as it was assumed that all recycling processes would be combined at the same location.
- No energy consumption was available for the sieving process.
- For reference, the environmental impacts were compared to virgin material and an alternative disposal route. It was assumed that the recovered fibre fractions can replace virgin glass fibres. Since no dataset was available in the Managed LCA Content database, a dataset from the ecoinvent database (version 3.11, cut-off) was used. Virgin glass fibre production in Europe was modelled using the 'RER: glass fibre production' process.
- For the alternative disposal route, it was assumed that the turbine blades would be co-processed in a cement kiln after disassembly based on literature information from Diez-Cañamero and Mendoza [1]. The respective life cycle inventory is provided in Table 4.3. Credits were calculated for the recovered energy and the limestone replacement.

Table 4.1: Life cycle inventory for the pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)

Pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste rotor blades	43.30	kg	No burdens (cut-off)	-
Electricity	11.54	kWh	-	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Rotor blades (shredded)	37.00	kg		-
Residual waste	6.30	kg	Commercial waste (composite material, other residues)	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table 4.2: Life cycle inventory for the sieving

Sieving				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Rotor blades (shredded)	1	kg	-	-
Electricity	-	-	No data available	-
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Fraction < 0.045 mm	0.17	kg	To replace virgin fibres (scenario analysis)	-
Fraction > 0.045 mm	0.07	kg	To replace virgin fibres (most promising, base case)	-
Fraction > 0.063 mm	0.05	kg	To replace virgin fibres (scenario analysis)	-
Fraction > 0.125 mm	0.71	kg	Commercial waste (composite material)	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table 4.3: Life cycle inventory for the current disposal route (co-processing in a cement kiln)

Co-processing of rotor blades in a cement kiln				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste rotor blades	1.00	kg	–	–
Electricity for crushing	0.22	MJ	assumption based on [1]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Electricity for shredding	0.11	MJ	assumption based on [1]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste for incineration	0.40	kg	Share from [1], to process 'DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H2O content)'	–
Waste for limestone substitution	0.60	kg	Share from [1], to replace 'DE: limestone (CaCO ₃ ; washed)'	–

B Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The results of the life cycle impact assessment are listed in Table 4.4. The normalized and weighted Single Score results are presented alongside the individual impact category results. The results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%) for data confidentiality reasons.

Table 4.4: Results of the life cycle impact assessment for the respective reference flow; for data confidentiality reasons, all results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Recycling approach	Material credit for substitution of virgin glass fibres (negative)	Co-processing in a cement kiln	Energy and material credit for substitution of energy production and limestone (negative)
Reference flow		1 kg of waste	mass of produced fractions	1 kg of waste	amount of produced energy and limestone substitute
Acidification	mol H+ eq	100%	-389%	132%	-246%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	100%	-100%	753%	-371%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	100%	77%	-44%	291%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	100%	801723590%	-48%	301%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	100%	-37%	94%	-189%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	100%	-14%	110%	-167%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	100%	12858029605%	-112%	440%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	100%	-4%	232%	-749%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	100%	0%	-54%	276%
Land Use	pt	100%	2%	-24%	226%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	100%	16173639928402%	-53%	273%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	100%	-1221648%	137%	-654%
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	100%	0%	90%	-177%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	100%	0%	-25%	230%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	100%	3507754%	-46%	266%
Water use	m3 world eq	100%	-38%	82%	-5%
Single Score	-	100%	-190502%	1725%	-1515%

The normalised results (in %) for material and energy credit are positive in some impact categories, which may seem counterintuitive at first glance. This is because the developed recycling approach generates waste that is incinerated. The energy produced during this incineration is credited when modelling the recycling approach. In some impact categories, this credit is higher than the impacts for energy and water consumed by the recycling approach. As a result, the numerical results for the recycling approach, which are used as a reference (as '100%'), are negative in some impact categories. Since the numerical results for material and energy credit are also negative (i.e. the same negative sign as for the recycling approach), the normalised results (in %) become positive in these impact categories, even though a credit is represented.

5. Scenario analysis

A scenario analysis was carried out to assess the environmental benefit of using more fractions of the sieving process. It was assumed that not only the most promising fraction would be used to replace virgin glass fibres, but also the two other fractions in Table 4.2 ('< 0.045 mm' and '> 0.063 mm'). This was modelled in a scenario. The results for the potential material credits are provided in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Results (EF 3.1 method) of the scenario analysis for the recycling of 1 kg of waste, all results are scaled to the results of the base scenario (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Recycling approach	Material credit for substitution of virgin glass fibres (negative)	
			mass of most promising fraction	mass of all three promising fractions
Reference flow		1 kg of waste		
Acidification	mol H+ eq	100%	-389%	-1607%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	100%	-100%	-415%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	100%	77%	317%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	100%	801723590%	3313790837%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	100%	-37%	-154%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	100%	-14%	-60%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	100%	12858029605%	53146522369%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	100%	-4%	-16%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	100%	0%	0%
Land Use	pt	100%	2%	7%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	100%	16173639928402%	66851045037394%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	100%	-1221648%	-5049479%
Photochem. ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	100%	0%	0%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	100%	0%	0%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	100%	3507754%	14498717%
Water use	m3 world eq	100%	-38%	-156%
Single Score	-	100%	-190502%	-787408%

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contributions

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Funding sources

This work was financially supported by the Ministry of Science and Culture (MWK) of Lower Saxony as a part of the grant number ZN 4173 for the project ReKon – Recycling concepts for high-quality mechanical recycling of previously non-recyclable waste streams of technical plastic components from the mobility, energy, electronic and electrical equipment (E&E) and health/pharmaceutical sectors.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge Aufwind (Aufwind GmbH & Co. KG) for supplying the materials used in this study.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information.

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